

APPROXIMATE CLOSED-FORM BUCKLING SOLUTIONS FOR THE OPTIMIZATION OF AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Buckling constraints are often neglected in the preliminary design of aircraft structures because the analysis is too complicated and time-consuming. Approximate solutions to local panel buckling problems are provided in this paper, and afford the opportunity to incorporate buckling constraints in the design with a small computational penalty. Two buckling solutions are presented. For panels with only axial loads, a closed-form expression for the buckling load can be derived, and the sensitivities can also be derived in closed form. When axial and shear loads are applied, a Fourier series can be used to describe the mode shape, and an eigenvalue problem solved to obtain the buckling load. Sensitivities can be found efficiently using the eigenvector associated with the critical buckling load. The constraints were tested using the ASTROS program developed by the Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories. The test case was a simple wing structure. The addition of the buckling constraint increased the design weight by over 67%. Both the closed-form and the Fourier series buckling constraints were implemented with less than a 30% increase in optimization CPU time.

KEYWORDS: Buckling; Design Methodology; Stability; Manufacturing;
Finite Element Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

In the struggle to produce preliminary aircraft structural designs quickly, many important design constraints are dropped from the design optimization process. Some constraints, such as flutter, fatigue, buckling, and detailed stress, are too time-consuming to calculate accurately. Manufacturing considerations are often ignored because mathematical expressions for the constraints are not available. This method produces a design that is often changed significantly after the optimization process, in order to satisfy constraints. It is the view of the authors that all important constraints should be included in the optimization problem, even if only approximate constraints or rules of thumb can be afforded. Approximate solutions to panel buckling problems [1,2] are provided in this paper.

For loads in a rectangular composite panel applied normal to the edge, Whitney provides an explicit closed-form solution for the buckling load. Since it is explicit, the sensitivities of the buckling load to the bending stiffnesses can also be calculated in closed form. For shear loads in a rectangular composite panel, an explicit form can not be obtained. A Fourier series representation of the buckled mode shape leads to a method that calculates buckling eigenvalues for combined axial and shear loads. Also, the orthotropic material axis does not have to be aligned with one of the sides. Both the closed-form method and the Fourier series method proposed are faster than a typical finite element buckling solution and sensitivity calculation.

ASTROS is a computer program [3] that performs optimization of aircraft and space structures. It has the capability to enforce a wide variety of constraints, however, it does not include a constraint for buckling. The program is very flexible, and allowed a buckling constraint to be added. The constraint types that were evaluated were done so by incorporating them into the ASTROS program.

The objective of this paper is to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the closed-form buckling method and the Fourier series buckling method, as applied to optimization of composite panels. Also, a simple wing structure will be designed with and without buckling constraints. The constraints' effect on optimization run time, the constraints' effect on design weight and construction, and buckling solution accuracy will be evaluated.

2. BUCKLING THEORY

A closed-form expression for the critical buckling loads NX_{cr} and NY_{cr} of a rectangular, midplane symmetric, composite panel, shown in Figure 1, can be found with the following equation from Whitney's text [1].

$$\pi^2 [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12}+2D_{66})m^2n^2R^2 + D_{22}n^4R^4] = - a^2 (NX_{cr}m^2 + NY_{cr}n^2R^2) \quad (1)$$

The parameters a and b are the panel dimensions, $R=a/b$, D_{ij} are the laminate bending stiffnesses, and m and n are integers. NX and NY are loads per unit length along the edge of the panel. Defining the following quantities allows calculation of NX_{cr} and NY_{cr} .

Figure 1. The buckling methods described in this paper are applicable to a rectangular, simply supported, orthotropic laminate of uniform thickness.

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{N} &= \sqrt{NX^2 + NY^2} & \bar{N}_{cr} &= \sqrt{NX_{cr}^2 + NY_{cr}^2} \\ k_x &= \frac{NX}{\bar{N}} = \frac{NX_{cr}}{\bar{N}_{cr}} & k_y &= \frac{NY}{\bar{N}} = \frac{NY_{cr}}{\bar{N}_{cr}}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

Substituting (2) into (1) provides the following equation.

$$\bar{N}_{cr} = \frac{-\pi^2 [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2n^2R^2 + D_{22}n^4R^4]}{a^2 (k_x m^2 + k_y n^2 R^2)} \quad (3)$$

The parameters m and n are chosen to minimize \bar{N}_{cr} . For given loads NX and NY on a panel,

the buckling eigenvalue $\lambda = \frac{\bar{N}_{cr}}{\bar{N}}$ can be found using (2). The derivatives of \bar{N}_{cr} with

respect to the design variables can now be calculated using the chain rule. For this paper, the design variables are the orientation thicknesses, t_{θ_i} .

$$\frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial t_{\theta_i}} = \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{11}} \frac{\partial D_{11}}{\partial t_{\theta_i}} + \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{12}} \frac{\partial D_{12}}{\partial t_{\theta_i}} + \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{22}} \frac{\partial D_{22}}{\partial t_{\theta_i}} + \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{66}} \frac{\partial D_{66}}{\partial t_{\theta_i}} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{11}} &= \frac{-\pi^2 m^4}{a^2 (k_x m^2 + k_y n^2 R^2)} & \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{22}} &= \frac{-\pi^2 n^4 R^4}{a^2 (k_x m^2 + k_y n^2 R^2)}\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{12}} &= \frac{-2\pi^2 m^2 n^2 R^2}{a^2 (k_x m^2 + k_y n^2 R^2)} & \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial D_{66}} &= \frac{-4\pi^2 m^2 n^2 R^2}{a^2 (k_x m^2 + k_y n^2 R^2)}\end{aligned}$$

Neglecting the stacking order of the laminate, the $[D]$ matrix is proportional to the $[A]$ matrix.

$$A_{kl} = \sum_{i=1}^4 (Q_{kl})_i t_{\theta_i} \quad D_{kl} = \frac{A_{kl} \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 t_{\theta_i} \right)^2}{12} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial D_{kl}}{\partial t_{\theta_j}} = \frac{(Q_{kl})_j \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 t_{\theta_i} \right)^2}{12} + \frac{A_{kl} \sum_{i=1}^4 t_{\theta_i}}{6} \quad (7)$$

The modes m and n that correspond to the lowest \bar{N}_{cr} often change from one design iteration to the next. If this happens, the buckling sensitivities from the first iteration will not be accurate as the design variables are changed to the values for the next iteration. An infeasible design is usually obtained. To obtain a converged design, the algorithm used in this study saved the two lowest \bar{N}_{cr} . The design was constrained from buckling in either of these two modes. Therefore, a mode change in the optimization problem did not allow an infeasible design.

The closed-form method is limited because only NX and NY loads are included. If shear loads are large in comparison to axial loads, the error will be large. Also, only four D_{ij} terms are used in the equation. D_{16} and D_{26} are assumed to be zero. If the principal material axes are not aligned with the panel axes, D_{16} and D_{26} will not be zero.

Complex buckling mode shapes can be described by a Fourier sine series.

$$w = \sum_m \sum_n C_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \quad (8)$$

The equilibrium equation satisfied by the sine series can include NX, NY, and NXY loads, and the effect of D_{16} and D_{26} terms. Thus combined shear and axial loads for a panel with material axes not aligned with the panel sides can be handled.

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 4D_{16} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^3 \partial y} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + 4D_{26} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x \partial y^3} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} \\ = NX \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + NY \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + NXY \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By integrating the moment equilibrium equation over the panel area, a matrix eigenvalue equation is obtained. This method is exactly the same as Whitney's method [2], except that Whitney only includes NX and NXY loads. The eigenvalues λ can be found in closed form if a small number of sine terms are used, but usually the lowest eigenvalue can not be pinpointed without knowing the values of the geometric parameters and the material properties. Instead, all λ are calculated using HQR solution method described in the book Numerical Recipes: The Art of Scientific Computing [4]. The lowest one is taken to be \bar{N}_{cr} . Sensitivities are found using a method developed for buckling problems by Kiusalaas [5]. The eigenvalue problem can be stated in the following form.

$$K\phi = \lambda G\phi \quad (10)$$

In this equation, K is the stiffness matrix, ϕ is the eigenvector, and G is a geometric matrix. By taking the derivative of this equation with respect to the bending stiffnesses, a simple solution for the eigenvalue derivative is obtained, because the geometric matrix is not a function of the bending stiffnesses.

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial D_{ij}} = \frac{\phi \frac{\partial K}{\partial D_{ij}} \phi}{\phi G \phi} \quad (11)$$

This sensitivity calculation is several times faster than finite difference method, but requires the calculation of the eigenvector, ϕ . This was done using the inverse iteration method described in Reference 6.

The limitation of the Fourier series is the cost to compute. A large number of terms (25 were used in this study) must be used in order to obtain accurate results. A 25 by 25 matrix must be inverted, multiplied by another 25 by 25 matrix, and reduced to tridiagonal form to capture the eigenvalues. A 25 by 25 matrix must then be solved several times by the inverse iteration routine to obtain the eigenvector of interest. This is much more work than the closed-form expressions of Equations 3-5.

3. BUCKLING SOLUTION VERIFICATION WITH NASTRAN

To evaluate the accuracy of the buckling eigenvalue prediction, the closed-form and Fourier series results were compared to finite element results. The finite element model that was used is shown in Figure 2. The NASTRAN program was used to perform the buckling finite element analysis. For each optimized design, the final laminate thicknesses and loads were analyzed with NASTRAN to determine the buckling eigenvalue. This eigenvalue was then compared to the prediction of the method used in the optimization run. Although NASTRAN is not guaranteed to provide the exact answer, NASTRAN and the other methods should be in agreement if all are accurate. Also, NASTRAN was chosen as a basis for comparison because it is typically used in the final checkout of the wing. If the optimization buckling theory matches NASTRAN, the design will be able to pass the final checkout before construction.

Figure 2. NASTRAN finite element models were used to evaluate the accuracy of the closed-form and Fourier series buckling eigenvalues.

4. ASTROS IMPLEMENTATION

The ASTROS program is modular. The main subroutines are called from a high level program written in the MAPOL language (similar in function to NASTRAN's DMAP language). The ASTROS MAPOL code was modified for this study. The main MAPOL modification is the iteration control, which checks both the standard ASTROS constraints and the user-defined constraints. In the original MAPOL program, all constraints are added to the database as soon as they are calculated. In the modified program, the constraints and the sensitivities are added to the database just before the design iteration. Other subroutines that could be confused by the extra database information never have a chance to read it. Three subroutines were added for each constraint type. One subroutine calculated the maximum value of the constraints. Another calculated the value of the constraints and stored them in the database. The third subroutine for each constraint type calculated the sensitivities of the active constraints to the design variables and added them to the database. The constraints and sensitivities for each design iteration were added to the database using the database subroutines provided by ASTROS.

Input of the constraints was achieved by defining a bulk data deck card for each constraint. For example, the buckling constraint for Element 13 was input with the following card.

CBUCKA	ID	L	W	ELEM
CBUCKA	1	24.4	76.2	13

This method for modifying ASTROS has not been tested on a large number of design problems, but it should be fairly robust.

The ASTROS buckling constraint can be defined as the inequality $\lambda \geq 1.0$. However, a constraint g must be modified for use in ASTROS, so that $g < 0.0$ when satisfied and $-1.0 < g < 1.0$ for the possible design variables.

$$g = -\frac{\log(\lambda)}{S} \quad (12)$$

The log function provides that $g < 0.0$ when the constraint is satisfied, and the parameter S is a constant to bound g such that $-1.0 < g < 1.0$. For this study, $S = 10.0$. The sensitivities of (12) can be obtained using the chain rule and either equation 5 or equation 11.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t_{\theta i}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}} \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}}{\partial t_{\theta i}} \quad \frac{\partial g}{\partial \bar{N}_{cr}} = \frac{-1.0}{S \bar{N}_{cr}} \quad (13)$$

The constraint g is a nonlinear function of the design variables, but this presented no problem for the optimization routine in ASTROS.

5. OPTIMIZATION OF AN SIMPLE WING STRUCTURE

The ASTROS Simple Wing Structure (SWS) was chosen to evaluate the buckling design method in ASTROS. The SWS is described in the ASTROS Applications Manual [3], and is shown in Figure 3. It consists of composite wing skins with three aluminum ribs and three aluminum spars. The ribs and spars separate each skin into four panels which were analyzed for buckling. The composite wing skins were subjected to Tsai-Wu stress constraints resulting from a simulated aerodynamic load. The wing tip was constrained to have a 0.05 radian wash out twist for the same aerodynamic load. Minimum gage constraints were applied for composite layers so that the lower bound was the ply thickness. Manufacturing constraints to eliminate interleaving, to control ply drop-off rate, and to control ply orientation percentage were applied. A complete description of these constraints is provided in a paper by Wang and Costin [7]. The objective was to minimize structural weight. The top and bottom skins were linked so that both skins have the same orientation thicknesses. The aluminum ribs and spars were not allowed to vary. Each orientation layer ($0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ$) in each element on the graphite/epoxy skin had a separate thickness design variable. The 0° direction was along the mid-chord spar.

Figure 3. The Simple Wing Structure (SWS) was used to evaluate the use of buckling constraints in a design problem.

6. RESULTS

Three runs were performed. The first had all the aforementioned constraints but not buckling constraints. The second had all the aforementioned constraints and included Fourier series buckling constraints on all composite panels. The third had all the aforementioned constraints and included closed-form buckling constraints on all composite panels. Resulting panel plies are shown in Figure 4.

No Buckling Constraints		
ROOT	ZONE 1	ZONE 2
	27 (13/4/7/3)	16 (8/2/4/2)
ROOT	ZONE 3	ZONE 4
	16 (8/2/4/2)	9 (4/1/2/2)
TOTAL PLIES (0°/45°/-45°/90°)		

Fourier Series Buckling Constraints		
ROOT	ZONE 1	ZONE 2
	42 (7/12/11/12)	25 (7/6/6/6)
ROOT	ZONE 3	ZONE 4
	40 (6/12/10/12)	24 (6/6/6/6)
TOTAL PLIES (0°/45°/-45°/90°)		

Closed-form Buckling Constraints		
ROOT	ZONE 1	ZONE 2
	41 (7/11/11/12)	25 (7/6/6/6)
ROOT	ZONE 3	ZONE 4
	40 (6/11/11/12)	24 (6/6/6/6)
TOTAL PLIES (0°/45°/-45°/90°)		

Figure 4. The resulting ply counts show that the buckling constraint significantly increased the design weight, and also made the laminate less complicated.

The design with Fourier series buckling was 67.3% heavier, indicating the importance of this design constraint. Also, it was closer to a quasi-isotropic laminate. Ply percentages and thicknesses are similar over the leading edge and trailing edge regions. The critical buckling loads for these panels of the final design were compared to NASTRAN. Errors were less than 2%, as shown in Table 1.

The design with closed-form buckling was 67.9% heavier than the run without buckling constraints. It was closer to a quasi-isotropic laminate. Ply percentages and thicknesses vary only slightly from the leading edge region to the trailing edge region. The critical buckling loads for these panels of the final design were compared to NASTRAN. Errors were less than 2%, as shown in Table 2, except for the leading edge tip region. This region is subjected to a relatively large shear load. Since the closed-form theory does not include this effect, a 4.4% error resulted.

Table 1. Comparison of Fourier series buckling results and NASTRAN buckling results show very little error.

	<u>ASTROS</u>	<u>NASTRAN</u>	<u>Error</u>
Leading edge root	1.005	1.021	-1.6%
Leading edge tip	1.716	1.738	-1.3%
Trailing edge root	1.014	1.038	-1.5%
Trailing edge tip	1.482	1.499	-1.1%

Table 2. Comparison of closed-form buckling results and NASTRAN buckling results show very little error, except when shear stresses are significant.

	<u>ASTROS</u>	<u>NASTRAN</u>	<u>Error</u>
Leading edge root	1.002	1.018	-1.6%
Leading edge tip	1.808	1.732	4.4%
Trailing edge root	1.014	1.028	-1.4%
Trailing edge tip	1.482	1.487	-0.3%

The computer VAX 8700 CPU time per iteration is a parameter that indicates the computational cost of each buckling solution method. The following CPU times were averaged over the first five iterations of each run, and include the time needed for buckling calculations, all other discipline calculations, and the design iteration calculations. It can be seen that the closed-form buckling method does not significantly increase CPU time. The Fourier series constraint significantly increases CPU time, but this increase can be justified when shear loads are significant.

Table 3. The computer run time per iteration shows that the closed-form buckling solution does not significantly increase computation time.

	<u>CPU time per iteration (seconds)</u>
No buckling constraint	16.4
Fourier series buckling constraint	21.3
Closed-form buckling constraint	17.3

7. CONCLUSIONS

Buckling is an important phenomena that should be considered in the preliminary design of aircraft structures. In this paper, two methods were presented that can successfully constrain a design to obtain adequate local buckling performance. Both the closed-form method and the Fourier series method had adequate accuracy for the Simple Wing Structure. The Fourier series method is more reliable, due to its capability to handle shear loads and non-aligned material axes. The closed-form method is much faster, however, and should be used when applicable.

The buckling constraints were added as subroutines in the ASTROS program. The flexibility to handle user-defined constraints is a distinguishing feature of the ASTROS program. The modifications to the overall control of the program were implemented to minimize conflict between standard routines and user-defined routines.

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